

Interview Aérocherche -Gilles Colaveri
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WP2. Investigating the conservation of WWII wrecks (land or underwater), and more particularly parts made of Al alloys.

- Presentation of the institution:

Aérocherche is an association created in 2013 by Gilles Collaveri, a business developer in the aircraft industry, in search for a structured background to share his passion of history of aircraft and aeronautics. The association operates mainly in the Southwest of France.

- The operating chain: from the wreck to the museum

At what stage or stages of the operating chain has (or is) the institution/ group / association been involved? Defining a recovery project? Integrating wrecks or artefacts from wrecks in the collection? Do they have direct input in defining the projects or just executing? What is their approach? Is it similar or different approach if different projects?

Aérocherche defines their own recovery projects, based on their strong knowledge of crash sites. Association has the initiative of research, depending on the interest of the aircraft (e.g., date). They are not necessarily focused on WWII wrecks, but always look for old aircrafts prior to 1950. Their interest is to share aviation history, and focus on the interest of a particular plane itself: rare type, famous pilot, etc ...

They base the choice of sites for excavations on archival research, testimonials, physical prospection and with a metal detector. Excavations up to a few cm undergrounds. They recover mainly small, separated elements, although there is also a 1 single entire aircraft project. They operate mainly in terrestrial context. All excavations are previously submitted to approval and authorization from the archeologists of the Direction Régionale des Affaires Culturelles (DRAC). Gilles insists on the fact that he is very respectful of this procedure, as it is not the case for all associations.

- Concept of "conservation": Do you think of long-term preservation/conservation of the artefacts you handle? How do you define long term? What does the idea of "conservation" mean to you for this kind of heritage? How would you want that heritage to be passed on to future generations? Has that definition shifted over time for you/the institution?

Gilles does not feel that long-term conservation is a primary concern for his association as parts found do not require specific treatment. He mentions that Aérocherche is only the tip of the iceberg: they always act according to the law, where many other associations do not. He feels that some branches of the DRAC turned a blind eye to this WWII aircraft crash sites, which is not a priority subject for them, as contemporary archeology is a brand-new topic for archeologists. But this is starting to change and

we now see publications and prospectings on WWII subjects, which is new and good. Gilles mentions for example that the Mont-de-Marsan air base has collections that are not registered with the DRAC.

- Who works on these collections (after recovery): conservators, technical staff (aviation background or not), volunteers? What training for these different stakeholders? Do they work in collaboration? Are they internal or external to the museum? What is the relationship between museum management / conservation and the people in charge of interventions directly? (Addition to Form A)

5 permanent members, as well as intermittent volunteers, all passionate about aviation.

The volunteers are mainly from Toulouse. Almost all have a connection with aeronautical environment, at various degrees (engineers, pilots, a cook, an airport baggage handler, etc...). Gilles initiates operations and manages the group during prospecting operations. Search for local information is on an individual basis, there is a lot of word of mouth.

The association has projects in connection with archeologists from 3 or 4 different DRACs. All regions do not have the same attitude (Gilles has experienced very different relationships from one region to another). He would like to see a unified approach from one region to another, (example: there is no general register of authorized associations). Gilles suffers from the image of prospectors with metal detectors; he can be refused authorizations, depending on changing interlocutors at DRAC.

- Conditions of conservation of the collection / artefact: aircraft in working order with regular maintenance / complete planes (or nearly) with or without preventive conservation / wrecks or elements of wrecks: exposed or not, kept in storage / outdoors (addition to Form A) ?

The association has a 40 square meters exhibition space in Aeroscopia museum, where they organize conferences, events with families of the crews, and rotating exhibitions, including frames called "history of the aircraft" = collages of small pieces on paper with texts and photos and included in a frame for presentation. Even a small part is an evocation and a support of the idea/image/story of the aircraft.

The association sometimes swaps various artefacts with other museums or municipalities, with the DRAC's agreement.

Most of the association's collections are small parts, there is no complete aircraft.

- Conditions of storage location (exhibition room or storage): rooms or hall? awareness about influence of climate on preservation? Monitoring or not of HR & T ° and their changes during the year (addition to Form A)?

In Gilles opinion, this approach is not primordial for his association.

Packaging: storage in boxes after classification.

The majority of the pieces are slag, pieces of burn metal, cartridges, they don't require any special packaging or attention, and it is not necessary to have specific conservation grade packing or storage as long as they are properly sheltered, which is the case.

Storage is either at the DRAC or at Gilles home (in plastic boxes in a dedicated shelter), except for very beautiful pieces that are kept in waterproof boxes. The boxes are classified by plane and are labeled.

Distribution is also based on the size and the possibility to exhibit the piece. The pieces destined to Aeroscopia are kept by Gilles until they are exhibited in the museum.

There is no climate control in the various storage spaces.

Gilles has not observed a change in the various parts' condition. Sometimes however, he has observed changes on the paint layers, such as discoloration.

- Reflecting on their own practice: do you feel that you know everything you would like to when it comes to managing this sort of artefacts ? What would be the aspects you would like to know more

about? Do you keep informed or in contact with other stakeholders in this field? Has your practice evolved through those connections?

His association is in contact with Aerorelic, ABSA and ANSA. He can see no particular evolution through these contacts. The interest is to share experiences, among other things about administrative procedures. Gilles wishes that official representatives could adapt better to the specificities of the field. For Gilles, the main purpose of the prospection and the recovery operations is to validate the aircraft type, the location of the crash, the trajectory of the aircraft and the background of the crash. For him, it's not such a big problem if the recovered pieces are little damaged in the process of recovery, as there are thousands of them. However, such damaging is rare.

Gilles is aware that there is a difference in the approach among archaeologists (that are often focused on medieval and antic artefacts), but he thinks they could adapt their thinking for WWII remains.

He thinks all Aircraft sites should be prospected and recovered, and more resources (both human and financial) should be allocated to aircraft recovery.

He questions the purpose of each of the stakeholders in the operating chain. It would be better if we could have a common orientation between associations and archaeologists.

Gilles claims to be guided by pragmatism and common sense, so he thinks there could be more flexibility from the official stakeholders, as he sometimes finds some branches of the DRAC very rigid on principles.

Association just wants to revive the history of aviation, with respect for laws and ethics (no trade to avoid looting, follow procedures for treatment of human remains).

Gilles points out the difficulties and the discord around the use of metal detector, he regrets the need for prefectural authorization to use it (it could be at a lower level: archeologists).

Gilles documents the context for the application of a prospection, he carries on interviews, and writes prospecting reports after the operation. Search for local information is on an individual basis, with lots of word of mouth.

- Conservation problem that may be encountered with Al alloys (questions and needs if there are any, or practices for solving these problems)? Does it feel like a priority concern regarding your corpus of WWII wrecks? regarding the rest of the collection (if relevant)? What type of treatment protocols are (or have been) carried out (addition to Form A)?

The association does little restoration.

Surface cleaning: removal of earth gangue by passes under lukewarm water, brushing the surfaces with soft metal brush, air drying.

Sometimes electrolytical treatment, but not required very often because corrosion is rarely observed.

On some parts, corrosion was initiated during fires associated with the crash, which results in crumbling appearance on the artefacts; Gilles applies anti-corrosion products such as application of "Rustol". But corrosion is not a priority.

Sometimes pieces with paint show ageing and color changes.

- Promotion of WWII aeronautical heritage, influence of the country's history in the conflict and the relationship to that history?

Gilles's focus is on the identification of aircraft and pilots.

He shares happily all aspects. He thinks it is very important to collect the last oral testimonies of direct witnesses of the conflict (these witnesses are the last ones nowadays).

He has prospected sites with wrecks from almost all nationalities, according to geographical context. He approaches in the same way French US, English and German aircraft.

He feels very strongly about the case of the Focke Wulf 190, a wreck located in the Lac de Grand Lieu near Nantes. This aircraft crashed in July 1943, when it was approaching Nantes airport after fighting with a B17. This wreck has been known for more than 20 years. It is located in a protected area. Gilles thinks that the tanks may still be full of oil and gasoline, which potentially could create a risk of pollution and for public health. Also, he thinks the pilot is probably still inside the aircraft. The pilot's brother wanted a decent grave for his brother. There was originally a refusal from the administration to plan the recovery of this wreck, as, for Gilles they were not interested in the project. Gilles would like now to work with the DRAC to explain the approach of the subject with archaeologists' and describe them the objective of the association that has been created to support the recovery project. He also had difficulty contacting the owner of the land. For Gilles, in addition to the former two arguments in favor of the recovery, this project could also reinforce French-German friendship, as there have been discussions between E. Macron and A. Merkel on this subject. The aircraft type has been widely manufactured (approximately 20 000 copies), but there are only about 10 or 20 complete aircraft available in the world. This one should in a particularly good condition and complete, which is very rare. For Gilles, this aircraft should be recovered and could be brought back to flying condition, as it would be the best way to serve the memory of the pilot. He speaks in strong emotional terms about the feeling one would have flying such an aircraft. He has already prepared the application to claim the aircraft's ownership and knows who he would like to contact to carry on the restoration.